

Dissociation of PbCl^+ in Aqueous Solutions and Related Thermodynamic Quantities

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The dissociation constant K of $\text{PbCl}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Pb}^{++} + \text{Cl}^-$ has been determined from 5° to 40° at 5° intervals from e.m.f. of the cells of the type :

where Q. H. stands for quinhydrone. Assuming B_4 in $\log \gamma_4 = -\frac{AZ_4^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} + B_4 \mu$ to be additive and independent of ionic atmosphere when $\mu < 0.1$ the thermodynamic dissociation constant K of PbCl^+ has been calculated. The value of ΔH° , ΔS° and ΔG° have also been calculated.

GARREL and Gucker¹ jointly calculated the dissociation constant of PbCl^+ at 25° from the e.m.f. data of Carmody² as well as Hannan³ and found it to be 0.0293 and 0.0289 respectively. Guntelberg⁴ from his own e.m.f. measurement found the value of dissociation constant of PbCl^+ to be 0.1 at 25° . From the conductance measurement Reighellato and Davies⁵ at 18° and Nancollas⁶ at 25° found the value of dissociation constant of PbCl^+ to be 0.0304 and 0.0255 respectively. The values at 25° differ a lot. It was therefore decided to determine values not only at 25° but also at a number of other temperatures.

A cell of the type :

where Q.H. stands for quinhydrone, was employed for this study. In such a cell hydrolysis of lead chloride as well as formation of PbOH^+ and its polymers⁷ if any would be negligible on account of the presence of hydrogen ion in significant amount. Since solubilities of quinhydrone and silver chloride in the experimental solution are very small, this is negligible, if any liquid junction potential due to them.

Experimental

A stock solution of hydrochloric acid (G. R. E. Merck) was prepared by diluting the concentrated acid with double distilled water. The strength of stock solution determined volumetrically⁸ (Borax method) and gravimetrically⁹ (silver chloride method) agreed with each other.

Lead chloride was recrystallised twice with double distilled water containing five drops of hydrochloric

acid (G. R. E. Merck). It was then dried carefully at 120° .

The experimental solutions were prepared by delivering the required amount of hydrochloric acid through a calibrated burette into a weighed and dried 500 ml measuring flask. To this solid lead chloride was added. It was then dissolved by adding double distilled water. When it dissolved completely the volume of the solution in the measuring flask was made upto the mark after it attained the room temperature. The measuring flask was weighed again. Buoyancy correction was made and the concentration in molalities of HCl and PbCl_2 were calculated. It may be noted that at different temperatures different solutions were prepared.

The experimental solutions were deoxygenated by passing pure nitrogen gas through water, presaturater and then through experimental solution.

Silver-silver chloride electrode was prepared by thermal electrolytic process as recommended by Harned and Ehlers¹⁰. Analytical grade (Renal, Budapest) quinhydrone was recrystallised and dried following the method of Harned and Wright¹¹. The electrode vessel, bridges were similar to those used by Prasad and coworkers¹². The cells were set up in the same way as done by Sinha and Prasad¹³. Measurements were made with a Tinsley Vernier Potentiometer. Duplicate experiments performed in each case generally agreed within 0.10 mv. In few cases at 35° and 40° differences went upto 0.20 mv. The recorded e.m.f. values are the mean of the duplicate cells. Experimental and other significant data are given in Table 1.

Stoichiometric molalities in mol kg^{-1} are denoted by m_1 in case of HCl and m_2 in case of PbCl_2 . Due

TABLE 1

Mixture of HCl and PbCl ₂ [†]		E in abs. volt	m _{Pb²⁺} × 10 ³	m _{Cl⁻} × 10 ³	m _{PbCl⁺} × 10 ³	μ × 10 ³
m ₁ × 10 ³	m ₂ × 10 ³					
Temperature—5°						
2.261	4.515	0.21945	3.572	10.347	0.9441	13.918
2.516	5.013	0.22410	3.874	11.403	1.139	15.277
3.016	6.020	0.23224	4.548	13.584	1.472	18.132
3.520	7.023	0.23900	5.100	15.643	1.923	20.743
4.013	8.010	0.24480	5.673	17.696	2.337	23.368
4.513	9.013	0.24997	6.219	19.745	2.794	25.964
5.008	10.037	0.25460	6.768	21.813	3.269	28.581
Temperature—10°						
2.260	4.508	0.23190	3.688	10.456	0.865	14.144
2.519	5.017	0.21870	3.985	11.520	1.032	15.505
3.020	6.025	0.22695	4.658	13.703	1.327	18.361
3.522	7.021	0.23385	5.270	15.813	1.751	21.083
4.019	8.025	0.23976	5.834	17.878	2.191	23.712
4.519	9.031	0.24498	6.365	19.915	2.666	26.280
5.013	10.039	0.24964	6.909	21.961	3.130	28.870
Temperature—15°						
2.269	4.526	0.20802	3.457	10.252	1.069	13.709
2.521	5.026	0.21302	3.733	11.279	1.293	15.013
3.024	6.030	0.22140	4.343	13.398	1.687	17.739
3.532	7.043	0.22846	4.888	15.463	2.155	20.351
4.034	8.043	0.23450	5.410	17.487	2.714	22.896
4.536	9.044	0.23974	5.836	19.416	3.208	25.252
5.040	10.053	0.24454	6.334	21.427	3.719	27.762
Temperature—20°						
2.269	4.524	0.20260	3.464	10.257	1.060	13.721
2.522	5.029	0.20750	3.752	11.303	1.277	15.055
3.025	6.031	0.21597	4.336	13.392	1.695	17.729
3.529	7.035	0.22303	4.822	15.386	2.213	20.208
4.035	8.045	0.22917	5.286	17.366	2.759	22.654
4.539	9.050	0.23448	5.658	19.247	3.392	24.905
5.042	10.052	0.23932	6.104	21.198	3.948	27.301

Continued...

TABLE 1 (CONTINUED)

Mixture of HCl and $PbCl_2$		E in abs. volt.	$m_{Pb^{2+}} \times 10^3$	$m_{Cl^-} \times 10^3$	$m_{PbCl^+} \times 10^3$	$\mu \times 10^3$
$m_1 \times 10^3$	$m_2 \times 10^3$					
Temperature—25°						
2.259	4.509	0.19697	3.386	10.154	1.123	13.540
2.511	5.012	0.20213	3.756	11.279	1.256	15.035
3.014	6.015	0.21071	4.302	13.331	1.713	17.633
3.510	7.007	0.21794	4.870	15.387	2.237	20.257
4.019	8.022	0.22406	5.197	17.238	2.825	22.434
4.519	9.019	0.22957	5.675	19.213	3.344	24.888
5.020	10.020	0.23441	6.040	21.080	3.980	27.120
Temperature—30°						
2.260	4.510	0.19237	3.649	10.419	0.861	14.068
2.520	5.017	0.19749	3.966	11.468	1.086	15.399
3.018	6.021	0.20618	4.538	13.577	1.483	18.115
3.519	7.021	0.21340	5.018	15.558	2.003	20.576
4.023	8.031	0.21978	5.543	17.597	2.488	23.140
4.520	9.025	0.22513	5.868	19.413	3.157	25.281
5.006	10.029	0.22996	6.257	21.292	3.772	27.549
Temperature—35°						
2.522	5.032	0.19205	3.626	11.180	1.406	14.806
3.024	6.036	0.20097	4.100	13.160	1.936	17.261
3.530	7.044	0.20832	4.622	15.196	2.422	19.816
4.038	8.056	0.21477	5.049	17.143	3.007	22.191
4.541	9.059	0.22040	5.456	19.056	3.603	24.512
5.041	10.056	0.22539	5.825	20.922	4.231	26.748
Temperature—40°						
2.526	5.039	0.18655	3.241	10.806	1.798	14.047
3.032	6.044	0.19541	3.616	12.692	2.428	16.308
3.538	7.053	0.20304	4.049	14.640	3.005	18.689
4.044	8.055	0.20968	4.499	16.599	3.566	21.096
4.552	9.066	0.21550	4.891	18.509	4.175	23.400
5.059	10.075	0.22055	5.137	20.371	4.938	25.408

to low solubility of $PbCl_2$ μ was confined to 0.03 ionic strength.

Discussion

Leaving out charges on the ions, the e.m.f. of the cells of the type :

is given by

$$E = E^\circ + \frac{RT}{F} \ln m_H m_{Cl} \cdot \gamma_H \cdot \gamma_{Cl}$$

Therefore

$$\log m_H \cdot m_{Cl} = \frac{(E - E^\circ)F}{2.30259RT} + \frac{2A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - B\mu \quad \dots (1)$$

where $B = (B_H + B_{Cl})$

In equation (1) E° is the standard potential of the cell i.e.

$$E_{cell}^\circ = E_{Q.H.}^\circ - E_{Ag \mid AgCl \mid Cl}^\circ \quad \dots (2)$$

The values of E° of quinhydrone have been used as recommended by Bates¹⁴ (taken from Ives¹⁵ book) and the value of E° of silver-silver chloride at required temperatures are known from the study of Harned and Ehlers¹⁶ as given in Ives' book¹⁷. The calculated values of E° (abs.volt) of cell at various temperatures are given below :

t°C	5	10	15	20	25	30
E°	0.48037	0.47939	0.47855	0.47785	0.47730	0.47688
	35	40				
	0.47669	0.47658				

The values of A on molality scale are taken from the work of Manov, Bates, Hammer and Acree¹⁸. The value of B in equation (1) as calculated by B. K. Choudhary¹⁹ from the e.m.f of cell (C₂) ;

as reported by Harned and Ehlers¹⁶ are given below :

t°C	5	10	15	20	25	30
B	0.456	0.444	0.460	0.480	0.490	0.476
	35	40				
	0.465	0.467				

It has been found from the work of B. Prasad²⁰ and coworkers that B in activity coefficient equation is

additive and independent of the composition of ionic atmosphere at least upto $\mu=0.07$ if the solution continues to be acidic and e.m.f. accuracy is not more than 0.1 mv. So the value of B in cell (C₁) containing a mixture of HCl and $PbCl_2$ will be the same as in cell (C₂) containing pure HCl.

Lead chloride in solution in cell (C₁) is assumed to be dissociated as

$$\therefore m_H = m_1 \quad \dots (3) ; \quad m_{Pb} = \alpha m_2 \quad \dots (4) ;$$

$$m_{PbCl} = (1-\alpha)m_2 \quad \dots (5)$$

$$\text{and } m_{Cl} = m_1 + m_2(1+\alpha) \quad \dots (6)$$

$$\therefore \mu = m_1 + m_2(1+2\alpha) \quad \dots (7)$$

For any particular cell an arbitrary value is assigned to μ . Since A, B and m_H in equation (1) are known hence, m_{Cl} corresponding to this value of μ is found from this equation. As m_1, m_2 are known so with this value of m_{Cl} , α is calculated from equation (6). Now a new value of μ is found from equation (7). The new value of μ is fed in equation (1) and the above process is repeated till μ is constant upto sixth place of decimal. The values of $\alpha, m_{PbCl}, m_{Cl}, m_{Pb}$ corresponding to this μ are taken to be correct.

The dissociation constant K of $PbCl^+$ is given by

$$K = \frac{m_{Pb} \cdot m_{Cl} \cdot \gamma_{Pb} \cdot \gamma_{Cl}}{m_{PbCl} \cdot \gamma_{PbCl}}$$

$$\text{Applying } \log \gamma_i = -\frac{AZ_i^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} + B_i \mu$$

$$\text{we get } \log \frac{m_{Pb} \cdot m_{Cl}}{m_{PbCl}} - \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} = \log K - B_1 \mu \quad \dots (8)$$

$$\text{Where } B_1 = (B_{Pb} + B_{Cl} - B_{PbCl})$$

The plot of L.H.S. of equation (8) against μ gives a straight line. The intercept at $\mu=0$ gave the value of $\log K$ and B_1 was obtained from the slope of the line. The plots corresponding to equation (8) at 10°, 25°, 35°, 40° are shown in fig 1. Similar plots are

Fig. 1. Equation $\log \frac{m_{\text{Pb}^+} m_{\text{Cl}^-}}{m_{\text{PbCl}^+}} - \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1+\sqrt{\mu}} = \log K - B_1\mu$
L.H.S.E. plotted against μ

obtained at 5°, 15°, 20° and 30°. The values of K and B_1 are given in Table-2.

TABLE 2

t°C	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40
B_1	0.916	2.785	2.451	6.575	7.000	12.224	5.100	1.272
$K \times 10^3$	2.48	3.01	2.19	2.52	2.57	3.91	2.01	1.18

Lead chloride is bound to be hydrolysed in aqueous solution, due to which some hydrogen ion will be present. This will increase the conductance and so the value of K in case of Nancollas work should have been higher than the present value. But his value is in close agreement of the present value. This is somewhat surprising.

The value of ΔH has been found from the slope of the straight line obtained by plotting the respective values of $\log K$ against $\frac{1}{T}$. The values of ΔG° at 25°

has been found from $\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K$ and that of ΔS° at 25° from $\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ$ (assuming $\Delta H = \Delta H^\circ$).

Reaction	$-\Delta H^\circ$ cal/mole
$\text{PbCl}^+ = \text{Pb}^{++} + \text{Cl}^-$	2100 ± 350
ΔG° cal/mole	$-\Delta S^\circ$ cal/degree
2170	14.31

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